

TRANSLATION AND INTERPRETATION: MY STORY

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Introduction. PhD scholar and Sessional Lecturer at the Australian National University, Fellow of the UK Higher Education Academy

Research interests: internationalisation of higher education, higher education governance and reform in Central Asia

BA from IELTE Program at the Uzbekistan State World Languages University

MA (Uzbekistan State World Languages University) and MA (Tsukuba University)

Lecturer of English Translation and Interpretation in Diplomatic Missions
Interpretation in Diplomacy

My experience Fluency in language is not sufficient

Interpretation for the Ambassador at various levels: official meetings, high level visits, negotiations and public lectures etc.

Interpreting speeches of Uzbek government officials at large state functions, receptions Interpretation in Diplomacy

Some are very sensitive topics with specific vocabulary Fast-paced nature of the work, should not forget the details, numbers in interpreting

High level delegations in narrow fields: engineering; pharmaceuticals, arts, tax and customs etc

Translation in Diplomacy

Diplomatic letters

Urgent visa and flight requests

Speeches of high level government officials

Subject specific proposals

Book: Religion of Peace There was a lack of reliable translation tools to and from Uzbek in those years Challenges in Translation and Interpretation Strong focus on training specialists in Asian, Eastern languages Thus abundance of specialists in this field Need for adequate training of translators/ interpreters from Uzbek to English/English to Uzbek Translators were attached to tourism, legal fields where the level of translation is repetitive Challenges in Translation and Interpretation Professional translators in Diplomacy mostly fluent in Russian and cannot handle official Uzbek The role of Uzbek language in translation and in interpretation School of translation and interpretation in diplomacy: mostly MFA diplomats did the translation for the government officials Rules and norms on interpreting at official dinners with high level delegation.